

The Trend of Adapted Recreational and Educational Sports Activities in helping the Physically Disabled to accept their Disability

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to find out the role played by recreational sports activities in the disabled to help the handicapped to accept disability. In the light of this study, we used the descriptive approach which is the most appropriate for this study. We also used the Likert disability measurement scale. The sample included 60 trainees from the vocational training center for the disabled. The sample was divided into two groups, one practice and one non-exercise. At the conclusion of this study, we concluded that the recreational sports activities adapted to the role of effective and effective in raising the level of disability acceptance of the disabled mobility, and we found that there is a direct relationship between the exercise of these activities and the level of acceptance disability.

Keywords: *Recreational Sports Activity - Disabled Movement - Accept Disability.*

INTRODUCTION

The issue of the disabled is considered a sensitive issue that has haunted human societies, both ancient and modern, to the point that the most capable and wisest systems in the world have not been able to eradicate it completely from their countries. However, the rate of its spread varies from one society to another, depending on the degree of interest and care that society gives it, starting from prevention to caring for its members, from all aspects (medical, psychological, social and educational), as caring for the disabled is considered one of the indicators of the progress of any society. Therefore, sincere thinkers working to serve humanity work hard to provide comfort for the disabled, which makes them capable of growing and building their personality, and rehabilitating them in the correct and sound manner, so that they become able to work and innovate. For these reasons and others, centers were established for the disabled category, and methods were invented that suit them, and educational material was developed that suits their levels. Among the areas that paid great attention to this category is the field of physical and sports activities, which provided modified and standardized programs, and methods of measurement and evaluation, to ensure good practice, and exploit most of the goals and objectives expected from this field. Adapted recreational sports activity is considered one of the modern and basic means of developing the disabled individual who practices it. The impact of this activity is in various aspects and levels, whether in terms of the individual's physical and mental abilities and readiness, and restoring some muscles that are considered almost atrophied, as well as in activating people with special needs and bringing them joy and pleasure, and developing them from a psychological perspective, which is often characterized in people with special needs by frustration, excessive feelings of deficiency, lack of a sense of security, and other characteristics mentioned by Dr. Klimek in his enumeration of the behavioral characteristics that result from disability. Practicing sports activity leads to getting

out of a state of stability, introversion, and isolation, and also contributes to integrating the disabled person into his society in an effective manner, and this has been confirmed by many recent studies. Adapted recreational sports activity makes the disabled feel the capabilities they have, especially since sports for people with special needs depend on classification in placing groups close in terms of capabilities and readiness to ensure fair competition and equal opportunities. This is what makes comparing the individual with his peers positive and possible, which ensures harmony between the personality of the affected individual and his environment and the environment in which he lives. Sports activity provides the opportunity for people with special needs to satisfy their hobbies and practice them in a constructive and appropriate manner. It is considered one of the necessary demands of the individual. Rather, recreation and play represent a therapeutic method for the psychological aspect of some people with special needs to overcome their emotional problems resulting from feelings of deficiency and lack of equality with others. The degree of adaptation for people with special needs is according to the extent of their acceptance of disability on the one hand and according to the society's position on it on the other hand. From this standpoint, the research problem emerged. This study is concerned with the role of adapted recreational sports activity in helping the disabled accept their disability. (Osama Riad, 2000, p. 23) This study that we conducted aims to know the extent of the importance of practicing adapted recreational sports activities for the individual with motor disability as a basic factor to compensate for his disability and accept permanent disability in Algerian society, as well as to identify the obstacles that led to the lack of interest in the latter in our country and to know the extent of Algerian society's encouragement of this category.

1. Problem:

The disabled are meant to be people who have a deficiency as a result of an organic, sensory, motor or mental disease, as this is due to genetic or acquired causes, as it may occur as a result of diseases or accidents, which prevents the individual from performing his basic requirements, which affects his natural growth or his ability to learn or practice work or his social adaptation. Disability produces psychological effects that may cause major changes in the individual's personality, so appropriate psychological care must be provided to the disabled. Of course, there is a difference between the disabled in their acceptance of disability, and certain personality traits may clearly emerge among them, such as dependency or severe anxiety, and lack of self-confidence... These traits arise from repeated frustration and failure to face the demands of life in a normal way. Some disabled people may resort to limiting regression, trying to compensate and integrate into the group. The school and family provide assistance to the disabled to get rid of these problems, such as benefiting from all their time so that they do not become idle, or deviate from the right path and become corrupted. Developing societies appreciate this direction, so they care about free time and include it in recreation. Adapted recreational sports activities have an important and impactful impact on the psychology of the disabled through developing their competencies and improving their performance by getting rid of psychological problems. It aims to guide the disabled in order to improve their abilities in facing problems, by referring to the obstacles that may hinder them. It also helps them to acquire good experiences and behavioral patterns, adhere to good habits, and develop good social relationships. (Al-Rusan Farouk, 1998, p. 50) Through our survey studies, and our field visits to a number of centers for the physically disabled, and our observations of the reality of adapted recreational sports activities within these centers, we noticed a neglect of caring for this aspect. Their practice of sports activities is almost non-existent, and this is due to those in charge of caring for these centers who are not aware of the importance of adapted recreational

sports activities. In order to raise this issue, we presented the problem, introducing it as follows: Does adapted recreational sports activities play a role in helping the physically disabled accept their disability? Through this problem, the following partial questions can be formulated:

- 1- Are there statistically significant differences in accepting disability between those who practice adapted recreational sports activities and those who do not?

2. Hypotheses:

- * General Hypothesis:
- * Adapted recreational sports activity has a role in helping the physically disabled to accept their disability.

Partial Hypotheses:

- * There are statistically significant differences in disability acceptance between those who practice adapted recreational sports activity and those who do not.
- * There are statistically significant differences between the impact of the social environment of those who practice adapted recreational sports activity and those who do not.

3. Reasons for choosing the research:

The disabled category is considered the most marginalized category in our society, as it is the category most exposed to various psychological problems. Through my observation of the lack of interest in the disabled from this aspect, i.e. psychological problems, I was prompted to pay attention and try to find solutions to alleviate these problems, so adapted recreational sports activity had a share in this field, through the disabled practicing adapted recreational sports activity by getting out of isolation and getting rid of various psychological problems.

4. Research objectives:

The objectives of this research can be limited to being an analytical study that shows the most important psychological problems that the physically disabled are exposed to within private centers on the one hand and the importance of practicing adapted recreational sports activities to get rid of these psychological problems on the other hand. To clarify more, this research aims to:

- * Identify the classification of the various problems that the physically disabled are exposed to within their centers.
- * Prove that practicing adapted recreational sports activities plays a role in overcoming the psychological problems that the physically disabled are exposed to.

5. Defining Concepts and Terms:

Several terms were mentioned in our research that require the researcher to clarify them and remove ambiguity and vagueness so that the general and specific reader can comprehend what is stated in it without difficulty or ambiguity, the most important of which are:

5.1. Recreational Sports Activity:

The meaning of recreation:

The word recreation is an English word that means renewal, creation and innovation, and there are theories and interpretations for it, as it surpasses in its concept the term "play", and recreation and entertainment are explained as an emotional reaction or psychological state and

a feeling that the individual considers before and during his practice of an activity, negative or positive, purposeful, and it is done during free time and the individual is driven by a personal desire and is characterized by freedom of choice in itself, i.e. recreation and entertainment more than activity, as activity is not an end in itself, but the end is that change in the emotional and sentimental state and the feeling of joy and happiness that works to charge the human battery to face life with its complexity. (Amin Anwar Al-Kholi, 2001, p. 75)

5.2. Adaptation:

Adaptation is defined as the adaptation of the living organism to itself and to the requirements of the environment and circumstances around it. It includes harmony and agreement for the sake of management and understanding instead of friction, conflict and destruction.

5.3. Assistance:

The plural of assistance (Saad) means assistance, aid. We say material assistance or material aid. In our research, we mean by assistance enabling the disabled person to achieve the greatest degree of psychological and emotional balance and to reach him to discover his talents and capabilities and use them to overcome the difficulties of life.

5.4. Disability:

Disability is the inability of the individual to perform a task that other people can perform. Disability becomes a disability when it limits the individual's ability to do what is expected of him at a certain stage, and disability is a state of physical harm or inability.

5.5. Motor disability:

A motor disabled person is a person who suffers from a degree of physical disability or a reason that hinders his movement and activity as a result of a defect, disability or disease that has affected his muscles, joints or bones in a way that limits his normal function, and thus affects the educational process and practicing his life normally.

5.6. The disabled:

Abdel Moneim El Hanafi refers to the disabled person as a child or individual who has abilities that are below the level and who has a defect or legal or functional deficiency that makes him unable to compete with his peers. However, Ahmed Zaki Badawi emphasizes that the disabled person is the individual who differs from those who are called normal or normal in physical, mental, mood or social aspects to the extent that it requires special rehabilitation operations that lead him to use the maximum that his abilities and talents allow. From these two definitions, it becomes clear to us that the disabled person is every person who is temporarily or permanently unable to use his abilities and talents as a result of being exposed to a physical disability.

5.7. Acceptance:

In language it means surrender, submission and tolerance, but in psychology it is defined by =Folke+ 1971 as the individual's position towards himself or others to appear satisfied with himself or others from the belief in the possibility of sensitivity or without being limited to criticism or punishment. Carl Rogers 1968 considers that this acceptance is necessary to change the situation in which the person is, i.e. improving his circumstances, saying that at the time I accept myself or others, I have the ability to change, and the more I am prepared to be simply

(me) with all the complexities of life, the more I seek to know and accept everything that is real in myself or others, the more I can change the situation for the better. Hence, it can be concluded that accepting disability does not mean surrender and submission to its negative effects, but rather it is a feeling of satisfaction towards the disability that results from it and which obstructs the individual's awareness of his condition with the possibility of compensating for this condition. (Jamal Al-Khatib, 1998, p. 30)

6. The Method followed:

Based on the nature of the study and the data that was sought to be obtained to know the extent of the impact of practicing adapted recreational sports activities on helping the physically disabled to accept their disability (15-18) years, we used the "descriptive method that relies on studying the phenomenon as it exists in reality and contributes to describing it accurately, and clarifies its characteristics by collecting information, analyzing it and interpreting it, and then presenting the results in light of it." (Ubaidat, 1997: 188). Based on this study, we conducted a survey study of the Center for the Disabled in Bouira in order to determine the study community, which is the category to which this study is to be applied through the chosen and appropriate method for this study. This community was chosen, consisting of students from this center who practice and do not practice sports activities. Thus, the research sample representing the original research community was extracted randomly and included 30 students who practice and 30 students who do not practice recreational sports activities within the center.

7. Controlling variables for sample individuals:

In order for its results to be independent of any other variables, we took into consideration controlling variables between individuals in the two groups to achieve balance between them in terms of age, nature of injury (acquired, genetic)

8. Statistical methods used:

In this research, the researcher relied on statistical tools represented by the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, percentage, and simple correlation coefficient.

9. Review of the Study Results:

Table 01: Shows the Values of the Arithmetic Mean, Standard Deviation, and T Values Regarding the Dimension of Adaptation to Disability.

Significance level	Degree Of freedom	(T) test		Physically disabled Non-practicing Activities		Physically disabled Activity practitioners		Transactions Statistical
		T-value tabulated	Calculated "t" value	Standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	
0.05	58	2.00	2.29	6.04	0.48	8.45	8.50	After adapting to disability

We note from the results obtained in the table that the arithmetic mean of the scores of the physically disabled at the level of the dimension of adaptation to disability for the category of physically disabled people practicing recreational sports activities reached 8.50 with a standard deviation of (8.45), while the arithmetic mean for the category not practicing recreational sports activities reached (0.48) with a standard deviation of (6.04). When comparing the arithmetic means of the two samples, it becomes clear that the scores of the category of physically disabled people practicing recreational sports activities were greater than the scores of the category of non-practicers, i.e. ($8.50 > 0.48$), and the standard deviation value

was large for the practicing category compared to the non-practicing category, i.e. ($8.45 > 6.04$), and on the other hand, the calculated T value was greater than the tabulated T value, i.e. ($2.29 > 2.00$), and this is at the significance level (0.05).

10. Interpretation and discussion of the results:

10.1. Interpretation and discussion of the results of the first hypothesis:

In order to verify the degree of validity of the first hypothesis, which states that there are statistically significant differences in the level of disability acceptance between the two samples (practicing and not practicing) of recreational sports activities, and this is what the results obtained from our analysis of the questionnaire results showed, and from this we can prove this hypothesis. From the above, we conclude that the physically disabled who practice recreational sports activities have positive acceptance compared to non-practicing ones, and this shows the importance and effective role of practicing these activities. This is what was confirmed by the study of (Bashir Hossam) through his discussion of the importance of practicing recreational sports activities in reducing psychological problems in the physically disabled athlete, where he reached the importance of recreational sports activities in removing the psychological barriers that hinder the physically disabled. From the results obtained and according to our observation of the differences, it can be said that the results of the first hypothesis have been achieved.

10.2. Interpretation and discussion of the second hypothesis:

It is a statistically significant degree of differences between the physically disabled who practice recreational sports activities and those who do not practice the same activities, on the one hand, and on the other hand, the difference between the averages was statistically significant at the same level, and this is in favor of the sample practicing recreational sports activities. Through the above and when we read the results obtained, it becomes clear to us that the positive acceptance of the physically disabled category who practice recreational sports activities at the level of the relational index dimension was greater than the level recorded for the non-practicing category. If this indicates anything, it indicates the important and effective role of recreational sports activities, which makes the individual accept practicing sports activities in general with motivation and positivity and recreational activities in particular to effectively invest free time and stay away from negative pests that harm the individual and society, as well as getting out of isolation and introversion and increasing the capabilities and social relationships that benefit the disabled individual and the society in which he lives. Therefore, through all of the above and its analysis of the results of the axis after the relational index, we conclude that there are statistically significant differences between the physically disabled who practice recreational sports activities and those who do not practice these activities at the level of this dimension, and this confirms the validity of the third hypothesis, which indicates the existence of statistically significant differences at the level of the relational index dimension between the physically disabled who practice and those who do not practice recreational sports activities, in favor of the category of practitioners.

- General Conclusion:

Loss of movement is considered a difficult matter for society in general and for the individual in particular, through many problems and situations that the disabled individual is exposed to through their interaction with those around them, whether in the family, school, or even within the scope of society.

The problem of loss of movement is not incidental in itself, but rather has a psychological and social nature, which necessitates providing all means that provide opportunities for the physically disabled, so that they can make their way in life to perform their functions and achieve themselves within this society.

Therefore, modern societies have rushed to pay attention to this segment and integrate it into society as an effective human wealth that can be invested and directed to form good citizens and strong elements in society by relying on all educational and rehabilitation devices and institutions to help these people. From this came the topic of our research, through which we aim to help this segment develop and grow properly, as well as impose themselves as normal people by proposing recreational sports activities to prove themselves. Through our analysis of the results obtained, we conclude the following:

- ⊖ Recreational sports activities contribute to eliminating introversion, isolation, escaping from reality and fear of it.
- ⊖ These activities help the physically disabled to prove their existence and importance in society.
- ⊖ These activities help the physically disabled in the functioning of vital systems well and effectively, such as: heartbeats, liver, and blood circulation, as well as maintaining bodily organs such as: hands and feet... from atrophy and thinness.
- ⊖ These activities strengthen social relations, social interaction, influence and being influenced, as well as accepting victory and loss.

CONCLUSION

At the end of this study, the purpose of which was to know the extent of the role played by adapted recreational sports activities in helping the physically disabled to accept their disability, and within the limits of this study, we concluded that there is a correlation between practicing adapted recreational sports activities and the level of disability acceptance, as practitioners have a high level compared to non-practitioners, and this is through the results obtained in the field study in which we adopted the "Likert" disability acceptance scale, while this scale was applied to two samples, one of which is practicing recreational sports activities and the other is not practicing them, and from it two partial hypotheses were formulated as temporary solutions, which are as follows:

- 1 - There are statistically significant differences in disability acceptance between practitioners of adapted recreational sports activities and non-practitioners.
- 2 - There are statistically significant differences between the impact of the social environment of practitioners of adapted recreational sports activities and non-practitioners. Through our analysis of the results obtained at the end of this study, which proved that there are statistically significant differences between the two samples (practicing and non-practicing) at the level of both accepting disability and the influence of the social environment, the results were all in favor of the practicing sample at the same level of significance (0, 05), which proves the validity of the partial hypotheses and thus accepts the validity of the general hypothesis.

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